

Original Research Article

In Vitro Introduction of Cameroonian Cassava Varieties Through Meristem Culture Technique

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Abstract

Availability of disease-free, high yielding cassava planting material is a challenge to producers. This study focused on evaluating the ability of improved and local varieties to be introduced for the first time *in vitro*. Meristem tip culture was used to regenerate *in vitro* plantlets of cassava varieties in Cameroon. Three improved (8034, 8061 and 8017) and two local varieties (black stem and Madame) were taken from the IRAD cassava breeding programme and locally from farmers' fields respectively. Five meristems were cultured per replicate (4) per variety. The number of meristem tips sprouting, rooting, the number of nodes and plant height were recorded weekly over a period of seven weeks. Data was analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23.0. One-way Analysis Of Variance was used to compare the means. Means separated using the Turkey test at probability level 0.05. Meristem tips of all varieties regenerated plantlets with vigorous shoots and roots. Sprouting began in the first week and mean number sprouted per replicate ranged from 1.32 (Madame) to 3.32 (8061). Root formation began from the 4th week and mean number ranged from 0.29 (Madame) to 1.00 (8061). Regenerated shoots of all varieties had average nodes ranging from 0.29 (Madame) to 1.55 (8061). Height of regenerated plantlets ranged from 5.88mm (8017) to 13.08mm (Black stem). All the cassava varieties tested can be introduced *in vitro* for rapid multiplication of planting material.

Keywords: Disease-free, *Manihot esculenta* Crantz, Plant regeneration, Rapid multiplication, Seed production

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INTRODUCTION

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) is the sixth most important crop in the world after wheat, rice, maize, potato and barley (Vincent lebot, 2010), with a world production figure of 277,102,564 tons (FAO, 2016). It is one of the major sources of food for humans and animals in most Developing countries (Scott *et al.*, 2000). It plays

a key role in food security in sub-Saharan Africa and it has been estimated to provide food for over 500 million people in the world (Abu *et al.*, 2006; Cock, 1982). Its roots are a rich source of starch, an average source of minerals and vitamins but a very low source of proteins, while its leaves are valuable in protein and minerals (Vincent Lebot, 2010) thus can improve the nutritional

status of consumers.

In Cameroon cassava is a leading crop in terms of annual yield both for cash and food crop categories. It is cultivated in all the 10 regions of Cameroon, with South, East, Southwest, Littoral and Centre being the main producers (Elise and Dapeng, 2012) with an annual production of 5,501,749 tons (FAO, 2016) contributing 2% to the world's share, thereby ranking Cameroon at the 12th position worldwide. On the other hand, Nigeria with same climatic conditions had production figures estimated at 57, 134,478 tons in the same year with a world share of 20.6% ranking it as first producer worldwide (FAO, 2016). Farmers in Cameroon cultivate both improved cassava varieties and landraces. Three improved Cameroonian cassava varieties which are high yielding, short cycled and tolerant to major pests and diseases have been released. These varieties include: 8061, 8034 and 8017 (Nformi and Comfort, 2012). Landraces (local varieties) are domesticated plant species which have become adapted to the local environment over time (Gibson *et al.*, 2000). Landraces can serve as the basis of future plant breeding programs despite their low yields (Allemann *et al.*, 2004). Both the improved varieties and land races have through the years been propagated conventionally by farmers through stem cuttings in the field. This method of cultivation enhances diseases accumulation, thus low yields and possibly extinction (Osei *et al.*, 2009). It is thus necessary to employ a measure to safeguard and increase production of these cassava varieties in Cameroon. The basis of agricultural production and nutrition of mankind is seed. Seed is, in agricultural terms, any materials that are used to plant crops (Mutlu, 2001). In seed programmes it is essential to initiate crop production with disease-free seeds since diseases affect the seed quality and yield. As opposed to the Quality Declared Seed System developed by FAO in 1993 and revised in 2006, crop species propagated by diverse vegetative structures such as setts, stem cuttings, tubers, vines, suckers and corms have only recently been declared in the Quality Declared Seed System (QDS) of FAO. With exception of potato and Musa species, vegetative propagated crops have received very little attention in the formal seed quality regulatory systems (FAO, 2010). Cassava as a vegetative propagated crop is prone to viral and bacterial infections which are of major economic significance (Legg and Thresh, 2014). Most cassava production programs in the world today make use of tissue culture techniques to overcome such challenges (Leva *et al.*, 2012; Habtamu and Wassu, 2016). Due to genetic variation, not all plant species respond positively to tissue culture techniques (Leva *et al.*, 2012). Considering the nutritive and economic value of cassava, it was thus necessary to introduce the Cameroonian varieties and landraces *in vitro* to increase production and enhance conservation.

Significance of study

In vitro plantlets of both improved and local landraces have been regenerated for rapid seed cassava production. This also gives room for *in vitro* conservation of both improved varieties and landraces.

Main objective

To enhance seed cassava production conservation of improved varieties and landraces in Cameroon through *in vitro* introduction by means of meristem culture technique.

Specific objectives

- Evaluate the response of three improved cassava varieties and two landraces to meristem culture technique.
- Evaluate the difference in response between improved varieties and landraces of cassava to meristem culture.

Hypothesis

Null hypothesis: The three improved varieties and two landraces of cassava will not respond positively and differently to meristem culture.

Alternate Hypothesis: The three improved varieties and two landraces of cassava will respond positively and differently to meristem culture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The plant material used in this study included 3 improved cassava varieties (8061, 8034 and 8017) and two landraces (black stem and madam) from the breeding programme of IRAD Bambui and farmers in the Bambui locality respectively. Twenty stem cuttings of each of the varieties and landraces were planted on a substrate (sand + rice husk + soil in the ratio 1:1:2) in 20 pots, a cutting per pot. The cuttings were allowed in the screen house to grow for six weeks and were irrigated as necessary prior to meristem culture. Shoot tips and stem sections (explants) were harvested with a sharp scissors and transferred submerged in water to the tissue culture laboratory. The explants were surface-sterilised successively in 30% sodium hypochlorite for 10 minutes, 70 % ethanol for 30 seconds and 2.5 % sodium hypochlorite for 15 minutes (Bihnchang-Ngwa *et al.*, 2017). Explants were rinsed thrice with sterile water and kept submerged in sterile water in a laminar-air-flow chamber. Under an alcohol-swapped binocular microscope (Magnification 40X), the meristem tips were

Table 1. Mean number of sprouted meristems seven weeks after culture

Varieties	Number of meristem sprouted (mean \pm SD)
8017	1.46 \pm 0.0922 ^a
8034	1.43 \pm 0.700 ^a
8061	3.32 \pm 0.863 ^b
Black stem	1.79 \pm 0.833 ^a
Madame	1.32 \pm 1.02 ^a

Means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to the Turkey test at $P=0.05$.

Table 2. Mean number of meristems forming roots seven weeks after culture

Varieties	Number of meristems forming roots (mean \pm SD)
8017	0.29 \pm 0.659 ^a
8034	0.43 \pm 0.504 ^a
8061	1.00 \pm 1.305 ^b
Black stem	0.43 \pm 0.634 ^a
Madame	0.18 \pm 0.390 ^a

Means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to the Turkey test at $P=0.05$.

excised with the help of a sterile hypodermic needle. Five meristem tips were cultured per replicate (4) per variety and landrace in test tubes containing 4 mls of MS medium supplemented with 0.1g L⁻¹ of Myo-inositol, 30g L⁻¹ of table sugar, 0.08 g L⁻¹ of Adenine sulphate, 4 ml L⁻¹ of 0.01mg ml⁻¹ solution of GA3, 1.5 ml L⁻¹ of 0.01mg ml⁻¹ solution of BAP, 2 ml of 0.1mg ml⁻¹ solution of NAA and 8g L⁻¹ of Agar at PH 5.6. The tubes were sealed, labeled accordingly and incubated in the growth chamber at a temperature of 25 C and 16 hours per day photoperiod. Data was recorded weekly over a period of seven weeks on: average number of meristems that sprouted, average number of meristems that formed roots, average height of regenerated plantlets, average number of nodes, average number of meristems that formed callus per replication to evaluate their ability to be rapidly propagated in vitro. . Data was analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. One-way Analysis Of Variance was used to compare the means. Means separated using the Turkey test at probability level 0.05.

RESULTS

The meristems of both the cassava varieties and landraces started sprouting in the first week and the average number of sprouted meristems increased progressively over seven weeks. The mean number of sprouted meristems ranged from 1.32 (Madam) to a maximum value of 3.32 (8061). Analysis of variance revealed a slight significant difference at $p=0.05$ amongst varieties and landraces (Table 1). The landrace (Black stem) performed better than some improved varieties (8017 and 8034).

Most of the cassava varieties and landraces (8061, 8034 and Black stem) started forming roots in the fourth week whereas 8017 and Madam started in the fifth week. The mean number of meristems that formed roots after seven weeks ranged from 0.18 (Madam) to 1.00 (8061). According to the ANOVA a slight significant difference was noticed amongst varieties at $p=0.05$ in terms of meristems forming roots, 8061 performed better. The meristems of Black stem which is a landrace performed slightly better than some improved varieties like (8017) (Table 2)

The average height of regenerated plantlets ranged from one variety and landrace to another. The analysis of variance showed that there was a slight significant difference at $p =0.05$ amongst the varieties and landraces. Black stem (landrace) performed better with a plant height of 13.08 mm (Figure 1).

All the five varieties (local and improved) had formed nodes after the seven weeks. The average number of nodes varied from one cassava variety to another. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a significant difference amongst the varieties with respect to average number of nodes. The average number of nodes ranged from 0.29 (Madame) to 1.55 (8061) (Table 3).

Meristems of all the cassava varieties formed callus from week one, Moreover, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a significant difference at $p=0.05$ in the mean number of meristems forming callus. The variety 8017 had the highest mean number of meristems forming callus (3.36) followed by Madame (3.29), Black stem (3.14) and 8034 (2.57) while 8061 had the least (1.68) as shown on the table below.

Figure 1. Mean plant height of varieties and landraces seven weeks after culture (mm)

Table 3. Average number of nodes formed by meristem after seven weeks of culture

Varieties	Average number of nodes (\pm SD)
8017	0.93 \pm 1.609 ^{ab}
8034	1.04 \pm 1.644 ^{ab}
8061	1.55 \pm 1.521 ^b
Black stem	1.08 \pm 1.308 ^{ab}
Madame	0.29 \pm 0.713 ^a

Means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to the Turkey test at $P=0.05$.

Table 4. Mean number of meristems forming callus after seven weeks of culture

Varieties	Number of meristems forming callus (mean \pm SD)
8017	3.36 \pm 0.951c
8034	2.57 \pm 1.230b
8061	1.68 \pm 0.863a
Black stem	3.14 \pm 0.803bc
Madame	3.29 \pm 1.013bc

Means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to the Turkey test at $P=0.05$.

DISCUSSION

Five Cameroonian cassava varieties comprising of three improved and two landraces were evaluated for five parameters which comprised of; number of sprouted meristems, number of rooted meristems, number of meristems forming callus, average plant height and average number of nodes of meristematic shoots.

All the meristems of both the improved cassava varieties and landraces sprouted indicating that it is possible to grow them *in vitro*. Meristems that remained green and increased in size one week after excision were considered sprouting. The slight significant difference noticed amongst the varieties could be attributed to genetic variation between varieties (Leva *et al.*, 2012). All the varieties equally sprouted implying that the hormone

combination of GA3, BAP and NAA was appropriate to promote sprouting. Thus was in line with the results obtained by (Kantha *et al.*, 1974). The performance of the local land race its yields could be increased after cleaning and this would increase the scope of farmers' preferred cassava varieties in Cameroon.

The meristems of the cassava varieties were capable of forming roots after the seven weeks. Even though there was variation in the time roots were formed amongst the varieties. Roots are an important part of an *in vitro* plantlet as it is very essential in acclimatisation. The probability of successful acclimatisation is very high with plantlets having a well-established root system (Xiansong, 2010). In this study, all the improved varieties and landraces formed roots implying they could be acclimatized *ex-vitro*. Apart from acclimatization, cassava being a root crop, root formation is of primary importance.

The height of the plantlets varied from one variety to another with respect to this study. This is in line with the report of Atehnkeng *et al.* (2006) who showed that there is genotypic variation in plantlets of different cassava varieties. The plant height in this research work ranged from 5.88mm to 13.08mm; lower than the results of simplice *et al.* (2018) which ranged from 16.8mm to 52.8mm. This could be attributed to the difference in hormone concentrations used in both studies as well as the difference in the genotype of the various cassava varieties used. Despite the low range in height, the varieties and landraces can still be rapidly multiplied *in vitro* for seed cassava production.

The formation of nodes by *in vitro* of regenerated plantlets is a very important phenomenon because it influences the rate of micropropagation (Smith *et al.*, 1986). In this study, all the landraces and improved varieties formed culturable nodes implying that they can be propagated *in vitro* with ease.

A callus is a disorganized proliferation of cells (Dodds, 1987). Callus formation leads to lost in genetic stability thus conferring some clonal variation (Jones, 1987). In this study callus formation started in the first week even though very minimal, probably due to the concentration of BAP that was used, as high concentrations (above 2.5mg/l) of BAP in a medium will promote callus formation (Rashmi, 2011). In this study callus formation was not too high probably because the BAP concentration was minimal (0.1mg/ml).

CONCLUSION

All the three improved cassava varieties and two landraces responded positively to tissue culture as all were able to form roots and culturable nodes. Despite this, some varieties performed better than others for all parameters measured. 8061 put up a better performance with respect to all the parameters followed by 8034, Black stem, 8017, Madame in this order. The performance of the landrace, black stem is a positive indication that it could also serve as a preferred variety to the farmers in Cameroon if given a little attention.

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